

Awareness of Stealth Marketing in Reality Shows: A Demographic Perspective

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Abstract

Stealth marketing is a style of promotion where a company conceals its involvement in a marketing campaign. The goal is to get people excited about a product or service without giving them the impression that they are being sold. This kind of marketing often outperforms traditional advertising because it creates a sense of excitement and authenticity. Customers should feel as though they discovered something on their own rather than feeling pressured to do so. Stealth marketing techniques include covert advertising, product placement, word-of-mouth marketing, and viral marketing. A company might, for instance, pay actors to advertise its product in public or arrange for product placement in a well-known movie or television show. The connection between the companies is kept secret in both cases, which gives the marketing an organic and real feel. This paper focuses on stealth advertising in reality shows and the awareness of stealth advertising with respect to age and gender as demographic factors.

Key Words: Stealth Marketing, buzz marketing, Forms of stealth marketing, Strategies, reality shows.

Introduction

The consumer is continually but subtly aware that they are being targeted by advertisements while using stealth advertising techniques. Advertising firms have developed a more "Under the radar" strategy to advertising since younger generations of customers are less enticed to traditional, overt advertisements. Customers are led to assume that they are responding to a promotion rather than an advertisement in order to achieve this. Given that most people do not want to be linked with overt product advertisements, promotional advertising takes a more understated approach to communication. Customers don't feel like they are being sold something this way; instead, they feel like they are learning. Stealth or covert marketing is the term for this strategy, which seamlessly integrates marketing operations into consumers' daily lives.

In order to raise excitement for its recently debuted camera phone T68i, Sony Ericson employed about sixty celebrities in ten New York cities in 2002, creating the first stealth marketing

campaign. As a result of the campaign's success, the companies created a platform for their products to build buzz in the market.

For many years, product placement has been a mainstay of Indian movies. The acclaimed movie TAAL featured Coca-Cola advertising. The Anushka Sharma-starring film "NH10," which explained how companies employ covert marketing to trick youngsters, featured advertisements for the Toyota Innova. Three commercials from Indian television networks were randomly selected, and each one was broadcast utilizing a different kind of stealth marketing.

(A.M. Kaikati, 2004). It was asserted in a previous study that peer group advice is the ultimate marketing tool and that word-of-mouth advertising continues to be the most effective strategy. Advertisers are using covert marketing strategies to cut past the clutter of traditional advertising.

Advertising professionals today encounter difficult obstacles when seeking to communicate their commercial messages. Customers are reportedly treated to hundreds of promotional communications each day, according to estimates from the advertising industry (Marsden, 2006).

(2006) Balasubramanian The fact that US restrictions on advertisements are less strict than those in other countries has been used by the author of the study to explain this tendency.

According to (Gensicke, 2006), undercover marketing functions as a promotional tool, much like imitation evangelists and brand pushers do in covert types of marketing. Undercover marketing, according to a plethora of recent studies, generates enthusiasm by recruiting volunteers to support the purchase of novel products that once more resemble a "brand moving ahead."

Types of Stealth Advertising

Product Advertising

This style of advertising is well-known and non-traditional, and it involves businesses and brands covertly promoting their goods via movies, television, and other forms of media. One of the most prevalent forms of advertising is the practice of companies paying media companies to place their products in films, television shows, and television commercials. For instance, a car manufacturer like Audi or BMW could persuade a media business to include one of their vehicles in a crucial scenario with characters killing the villain after exiting a vehicle.

Undercover Marketing

In covert marketing strategies, a new product is unmistakably introduced to the buyer without it appearing to be an advertisement. It calls for originality and nontraditional marketing techniques. A clever salesperson will constantly try to promote their goods covertly. Even if you hear other people talking about a new product, it is still stealth marketing.

A reality show is a category of television program that showcases how regular people behave in real-world situations. These programs are frequently produced by people who are supposed to mirror everyday life. Reality TV is essentially unscripted television that is based on actual events or situations and does not use actors. Most reality shows have a host who runs the show or a narrator who tells the story or sets the scene for what will happen.

Data and Methodology

The research paper is based on the data collected from both primary data and secondary data. 790 respondents provided the primary data that was gathered. The sample's perceptions of the effects of covert marketing of goods advertised on reality shows were captured in the questionnaire's replies. For this, a well-structured questionnaire was prepared. The demographic information of the respondents was gathered in the questionnaire's first section. The majority of the questionnaire's questions used Likert scales. When a person is in the cognitive stage, they are developing their belief and knowledge systems about the product. As a result, the statements that tested the respondent's assessment of whether or not the stealth marketing of products caught their attention were included in the Cognitive Stage Scale. Statements like "I was able to recognize the brand's presence" and "I could recall the brand positioning upon seeing the promotion" were included on this scale.

A different method of product marketing is stealth marketing. This aids in better clearing the clutter and giving the brand a more significant and potent association. The tangible proof presented in the setting strengthens the brand club and enables potential customers to more easily associate themselves with the brand. The goal of this study is to better understand how stealth marketing affects the client acquisition process at three different levels. In order to improve the use of stealth marketing and better serve the general public, the academic community, industry stakeholders, and the general public will benefit from a greater understanding of this practice provided by this study.

Analysis and Interpretation of Results

Demographic analysis

Graph: Gender Composition

Chart 1: Gender composition of sample

Interpretation: Out of the total sample of seven ninety, three eighty-six were male respondents whereas 404 were female respondents

Graph: Age composition

Chart 2: Age composition of sample

Interpretation: Out of the total sample of seven hundred and ninety respondents, 386 respondents were of the age group 18-27 whereas 404 respondents were of the age group 28-35

Independent sample T-Test

Group Statistics					
	Respondent's gender	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
CS_summated	Male	386	3.2648	.63757	.03245
	Female	404	3.3683	.59692	.02970

Group statistics – Gender - CS

Independent Samples Test	
Levene's Test for Equality of Variances	t-test for Equality of Means

		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
									Lower	Upper
CS_summated	Equal variances assumed	.251	.616	-2.358	788	.019	-.10355	.04392	-.18977	-.01733
	Equal variances not assumed			-2.354	778.356	.019	-.10355	.04399	-.18990	-.01720

T-statistic for Gender - CS

Interpretation: Levene's test has a significance value of 0.616, which is higher than 0.5. As a result, Levene's test's null hypothesis cannot be accepted. Equal variances are therefore assumed. As a result, the significant value of 0.19 for the independent sample t-test should be taken into account. Less than 0.5 applies to this value. As a result, the independent sample t-test's null hypothesis is disproved. As a result, there is a big discrepancy between the genders in CS. After looking at the statistical data it has been found that females perceive more than males at the cognitive stage.

Independent sample T-Test

Group Statistics					
	Respondent's age	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
CS_summated	18-26	386	3.2648	.63757	.03245
	27-35	404	3.3683	.59692	.02970

Group statistics – Age - CS

Independent Samples Test										
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						
		F	Sig.	T	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
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The study discovered that respondents between the ages of 28 and 35 were seen more favorably for the cognitive stage after looking at the group statistics table.

Findings

Independent sample t-test was conducted in order to check the effects of gender on the cognitive stage scale

A p-value of 0.019 was seen. The independent sample t-test's null hypothesis was rejected since this result was less than 0.05. This suggested that there was a sizable gender difference in the perception of the cognitive stage scale. The group statistics table revealed that women have a higher favorable opinion of the cognitive stage scale. The study also discovered that, in comparison to men, women are better able to recognize brand presence and form belief systems about it in recent investigations.

Independent sample t-test was conducted in order to check the effects of age on the cognitive stage scale

A p-value of 0.019 was discovered. The independent sample t-test's null hypothesis was rejected since this result was less than 0.05. This suggested that there was a sizable age-related variance in perception of the cognitive stage scale. According to the group data table, respondents in the age range of 27 to 35 have a more favorable opinion of the cognitive stage scale. This can be due to the fact that the majority of these respondents have completed their schooling and are employed, which has led to more exposure and easier brand recognition.

Conclusions

- Different levels of perspective regarding how people believe about themselves when their demographic factors are taken into account have been noted.

- Female products should put more of an emphasis on stealth marketing for promotion since it has been observed that females are more susceptible to it.
- Reality television is a fantastic medium for covert marketing.

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